

Does Investment in Education and Training Enhance Productivity Growth? Evidence from European Union Countries

Iulia Siedschlag^{1,2} and Juan Durán^{1,2}

1. Economic Analysis, Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI)
Dublin, Ireland
2. Department of Economics, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

Summary

1. This policy brief summarises recent research-based evidence on the direct and indirect effects of investment in training on labour productivity growth in European Union countries.
2. Results indicate that training boosts significantly labour productivity with the effect being strongest in industries with a higher intensity of investment in training.
3. Investment in training enhances the effects of other intangible assets on labour productivity, especially in business services.
4. Indirect effects of investment in training on productivity growth are mainly driven by synergies between investment in training and organisational capital.
5. From a policy perspective, the results of this research highlight the importance of measuring investment in on-the-job training and in other intangible assets to inform knowledge-based pro-growth policies.

1. Introduction

Human capital accumulation as a result of investment in education is an important driver of productivity, innovation and long-term economic growth. However, the effects of investment in education and skills on these economic outcomes are likely to be underestimated for two reasons (Acemoglu, 2009; O'Mahony, 2012). First, existing evidence does not account for the fact that

human capital accumulation continues after the completion of formal education. Second, while standard measures of human capital are based on the number years of schooling (quantitative measures), there are significant differences in the quality of schools and teachers which are reflected in the quality of human capital.

This policy brief summarises a research paper by Siedschlag and Durán (2025), part of the EFFEct project. This research generates new

knowledge to fill the evidence gap with respect to the direct and indirect effects of investment in on-the-job training on productivity growth in European Union countries.

2. Data and Methodology

This research uses data from the 2025 release of the EUKLEMS and INTANProd databases including capital and labour accounts as well data on intangible assets for EU 27 countries, the UK and the US over the period 1995-2021.¹ The empirical analysis uses data for all sectors excluding public administration and defense.

The empirical strategy is informed by a production function theoretical framework. Specifically, a Cobb-Douglas production function augmented with intangible inputs is estimated. The baseline model estimates the annual growth of labour productivity in a given country and sector, as a function of technical efficiency and annual changes in the accumulation of tangible (physical) capital, training capital and other intangible capital assets. Additional control variables include time-invariant country-industry specific effects and year-specific effects controlling for common macroeconomic shocks. To explore the heterogeneity of the effects of training on productivity growth, a difference-in-differences empirical approach following Rajan and Zingales (1998) is used. The causal effects are identified through an instrumental variables (IV) approach.

3. Results

The average intensity of training capital over the analysed period, 1995-2021, is the highest

in Ireland, Denmark, and Finland and the lowest in Greece, Latvia and Cyprus. Across sectors, the highest average intensity of training capital is the highest in Education, Professional scientific and technical activities, other services, and Financial and insurance activities, and the lowest in Real estate activities, and the sectors combining agriculture, forestry and fishing, mining and quarrying.

The baseline estimates indicate that in European Union countries, over the analysed period, the accumulation of intangible capital has been the main driver of labour productivity growth. Taken together, the results of this research indicate that productivity growth is stronger in industries with a higher intensity of investment in training.

Furthermore, the evidence shows that investment in training enhances the effects of the accumulation of other intangible assets such as software and databases, innovative property and economic competences on labour productivity growth. This complementarity is strongest in business services, and it is driven mainly by the synergy between investment in training and organisational capital.

These results are robust to alternative measures of the intensity of investment in training and are not driven by any particular country or industry.

4. Policy Recommendations

The results of this research highlight the importance of measuring investment in

¹ See Bontadini et al. (2023) for a detailed description of the EUKLEMS and INTANProd data bases.

training and in other intangible assets to inform knowledge-based pro-growth policies. Integrating these measures into the System of National Accounts and international coordination on data production and data collection by national statistics offices are crucially important.

Education and training policies need to adapt to changing demands for skills in the context of rapid technological and demographic changes and the transition to low-carbon economies.

At firm level, investment in on-the-job training plays an important role for skilling, re-skilling and upskilling of the workforce to adapt to changing skills needs.

At Member State level, coordination and collaboration across all government departments and agencies as well as between government, industry stakeholders and educational institutions are essential to developing skills and training strategies for a workforce prepared for the challenges of digital transformation, demographic changes and low-carbon economies.

The European Commission is well placed to provide international expertise and technical assistance to support Member States to design national education and training strategies to respond to changing skills needs in the context of these challenges.

What is EFFEct?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

References

- Acemoglu, D. (2009). *Introduction to Modern Economic Growth*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Bontadini, F., Corrado, C., Haskel, J., Iommi, M., & Jona-Lasinio, C. (2023). EUKLEMS & INTANProd: industry productivity accounts with intangibles—Sources of growth and productivity trends: methods and main measurement challenges. The Luiss Lab of European Economics. <https://euklems-intanprod-llee.luiss.it/>
- O'Mahony, M. (2012). Human capital formation and continuous training: Evidence for EU countries. *Review of Income and Wealth*, 58(3), 531–549.
- Rajan, R. G., & Zingales, L. (1998). Financial dependence and growth. *The American Economic Review*, 88(3), 559–586.

Further Information:

Siedschlag I., and Durán Vanegas, J. (2025) The Effects of Investment in Education and Training on Productivity Growth in the European Union, ESRI Working Paper 802, Dublin: ESRI
<https://www.esri.ie/publications/the-effects-of-investment-in-education-and-training-on-productivity-growth-in-the>

**Funded by
the European Union**

EFFEct is funded by the European Union in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101129146). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online: www.effect-project.eu

Follow us on X: [@EFFect_Proj](https://twitter.com/EFFect_Proj)

Follow us on LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/EFFect-project/